

CRYSTALLINE COMPONENTS OF THE BARK OF *PRUNUS PUDDUM*, ROXB. PART I. IDENTITY OF PUDDUMETIN WITH GENKWANIN

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Three crystalline products have been isolated from the bark of *Prunus puddum*, Roxb. These have m.p. 278-80°, 150-52° and 237-38° respectively. The compound, m.p. 278-80°, which has been named Puddumetin, now appears to be identical with genkwanin (7-methylapigenin), isolated from the Chinese drug, 'Yuen hua'.

Prunus puddum, Roxb. (N. O. Rosaceae) (*Vern.* Phaja, Pajia, Paddam) is a middle-sized or large tree and is often cultivated in the outer Himalayas from the Sutlej to Sikkim, mostly between 2,500 and 7,000 ft., in the Khasi Hills, Manipur and also in Upper Burma (4,000-6,000 ft.). It flowers early in winter and in spring and the flowers are white, pink or crimson. Its wood is pale red in colour and the bark peels off in horizontal strips. The bark of *P. puddum*, used in this investigation, was supplied by Messrs. G. Ghosh & Co. of Darjeeling.

Three crystalline products have been isolated from the ethereal extract of the bark:

- (i) A bright yellow light crystalline solid, m.p. 278-80°. It has been named *Puddumetin* (*Science & Culture*, 1942-43, 8, 463).
- (ii) A hard shining colourless crystalline substance, m.p. 150-52°.
- (iii) Shining light yellow needles, m.p. 237-38°. It has been named *Prunusetin*, (Chakravarti and Bhar, *Science & Culture*, 1942-43, 8, 498).

The constitution of puddumetin is discussed in this paper.

Analytical data of puddumetin are in agreement with the formula $C_{16}H_{12}O_5$. It contains two phenolic OH groups and it forms a colourless diacetyl derivative, m.p. 198-99°. Methoxyl estimation shows the presence of one OMe group, hence puddumetin is $C_{15}H_7O_2(OMe)(OH)_2$.

Puddumetin is insoluble in alkali carbonate and bicarbonate solutions, but dissolves in aqueous solutions of caustic alkalis. On acidification of the alkaline solution the original substance is precipitated. On reducing a cold alcoholic solution of the substance with magnesium and hydrochloric acid a deep orange colour is produced. These reactions indicate that puddumetin is most probably a flavone. The molecular formula of puddumetin agrees with monomethoxy-dihydroxyflavone. Hence it can be represented by the partial formula (I).

On methylation with methyl iodide puddumetin gives a monomethyl ether, which can be acylated to a monoacetyl derivative, m.p. 194-96°. One of the hydroxyl groups possesses weak phenolic properties and it is found that puddumetin monomethyl ether does not readily dissolve in caustic alkali solution. It is well known that a hydroxyl group in position 5 of the benzopyrone nucleus possesses weak phenolic properties and generally resists methylation. Hence it may be inferred that one of the OH groups of puddumetin is situated at position 5.

Puddumetin is unaffected when a rapid current of air is aspirated through its alkaline solution for more than 2 hours. This excludes the possibility of OH group being present in position 3 of the pyrone ring. The possibility of a methoxyl group being present in 2 position is not, however, definitely excluded. Perkin found that galangin monomethyl ether undergoes aerial oxidation in alkaline solution with formation of benzoic acid and phloroglucinol. Other workers, however, consider that compounds with methoxyl group in position 3 are stable to aerial oxidation in alkaline solution. Thus Bose and Dutta (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 17, 46) found that erianthin is stable to aerial oxidation (*cf.* also Bose *et al.*, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 18, 141; 1939, 16, 184).

p-Hydroxyacetophenone (m.p. 102-5°) has been obtained by the hydrolysis of puddumetin with alcoholic potash. Consequently puddumetin is a *p*-hydroxylated flavone (II).

On demethylation with hydriodic acid puddumetin gives a pale yellow crystalline compound (m.p. 344-46°), which seems to be identical in properties and m.p. with apigenin. The m.p. of apigenin is recorded in literature as 343° (Perkin and Everest, "The Natural Organic Colouring Matters"), 347-48° ("Handbuch der Pflanzenanalyse," edited by Klein). Further on acetylation the demethylated product gives a triacetate (m.p. 181-82°) (apigenin triacetate also melts at 181-82°). Hence puddumetin is 7-methylapigenin or genkwanin (II). This conclusion is further supported by the fact that puddumetin monomethyl ether and monoacetyl puddumetin monomethyl ether have the same m.p.s as apigenin dimethyl ether (m.p. 171-72°) and monoacetyl apigenin dimethyl ether (m.p. 195-96°) respectively.

The probability that puddumetin is identical with genkwanin was emphasised by Venkataraman (*Science & Culture*, 1942-43, 8, 464), but in absence of an authentic specimen of genkwanin and its appropriate derivatives, and in view of the fact that puddumetin melts at a temperature 6-8° lower than the m.p. of genkwanin, it was thought desirable to study the reactions and properties of our compound in greater detail.

Further work on the constitution of prunusetin (m.p. 237-38°) and of the compound (m.p. 150-52°) is in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL

* The powdered bark (600 g.) was extracted with ether in a Soxhlet apparatus for 16 hours. The orange-yellow ethereal solution was concentrated to approximately one-tenth its volume and allowed to stand overnight. A yellow solid separated, which was filtered and the filtrate evaporated until ether was completely removed. A reddish oil which solidified on keeping to a gelatinous mass was obtained.

(i) *Isolation of Puddumetin*.—The yellow solid, obtained above, consists of two substances, one being more soluble in alcohol. It was crystallised from a small amount of alcohol, the crystals separating melt at 210-20° and the insoluble residue crystallises again from rectified spirit as yellow needles, m.p. above 270°. The fraction having the lower melting point crystallises from glacial acetic acid as light yellow needles, m.p. 225-30° and the fraction having the higher melting point crystallises from glacial acetic acid as deep yellow silky needles, m.p. 278-80° (A).

The oily residue, obtained by evaporating the ethereal filtrate, was dissolved in about four times its volume of hot rectified spirit and the solution was allowed to stand. The solid separating was collected and the filtrate was diluted with water when a fresh crop of solid was obtained. Much difficulty was experienced in filtering this solid due to the presence of slimy

* The constituents have been isolated in collaboration with Mr. Bankim Chandra Bera.

matter. By repeating this procedure the maximum amount of solid was collected and the dilute alcoholic filtrate was rejected. The solids obtained were dried and repeatedly refluxed with benzene when they mostly dissolved, leaving small quantities of yellow or brown residues. The residues were all crystallised from glacial acetic acid, when light brown crystals were obtained, m.p. 225-30°. These together with the light yellow crystals, m.p. 225-30°, obtained above, were then extracted several times with boiling acetone and the residue finally left had m.p. above 275° (B). The acetone solution on evaporation gave a solid, m.p. 225-30°. This was extracted thrice with small quantities of boiling ethyl acetate and the ethyl acetate-insoluble residue (m.p. above 275°) was mixed with residue (B) and crystallised from glacial acetic acid as deep yellow silky needles, m.p. 278-80°, identical with the product (A), total yield 0.04% of the weight of the dry bark.

(ii) *Isolation of a compound* m.p. 150-52°.—The benzene solution, obtained above, deposited crystals on standing overnight and further crop of crystals was obtained on concentrating the benzene mother-liquors. These crystals were repeatedly recrystallised from benzene and then from rectified spirit, m.p. 125-30°. On recrystallisation from glacial acetic acid the m.p. rose to 147-50°. Finally it was crystallised from chloroform, when hard lustrous crystals were obtained, m.p. 150-52°. A further crop of crystals, m.p. 150-52°, was obtained from the benzene and chloroform mother-liquors by repeating the above process. Total yield, 0.8% of the weight of the dry bark.

From the above mother-liquors on evaporation of the solvents a yellow solid (m.p. 123-24° with contraction at 121°) was left.

(iii) The ethyl acetate solution, obtained above, on concentration and cooling deposited crystals, which on repeated crystallisation from ethyl acetate and finally from glacial acetic acid, melt at 237-38°. This has been named *Prunasetin* (Chakravarti and Bhar, *loc. cit.*)

Puddumetin was obtained as deep yellow silky needles, m.p. 278-80°. It is sparingly soluble in ether, benzene and chloroform. It is insoluble in cold alkali carbonate and bicarbonate solutions but is very readily soluble in cold caustic alkali solutions giving yellow colour. An alcoholic solution of the substance gives a brown-violet colouration to ferric chloride solution. It produces an orange colour when reduced in alcoholic solution with magnesium and hydrochloric acid. (Found in a sample dried over P₂O₅ in *vacuum* at 120-30°: C, 67.94; H, 4.46; OMe, 11.35. C₁₅H₉O₄.OMe requires C, 67.6; H, 4.23; OMe, 10.92 per cent).

Diacetylpuddumetin was obtained from puddumetin with acetic anhydride and pyridine. It crystallises from dilute acetic acid and rectified spirit as colourless silky needles, m.p. 198-99°. (Found in a sample dried over P₂O₅ in *vacuum* at 120-30°: C, 65.7; H, 4.53; OMe, 8.15. C₁₉H₁₃O₆.OMe requires C, 65.21; H, 4.35; OMe, 8.42 per cent). The m.p.s of diacetyl genkwanin have been recorded as 197-98° (Mahal and Venkataraman, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 569) and 196° (Nakano and Tseng, *J. Chem. Soc. Jap.*, 1932, No. 602, 343, 1933, No. 608, 905).

Puddumetin monomethyl ether was prepared by refluxing for 3 hours a solution of puddumetin (0.1 g.) in dry acetone with methyl iodide (10 c.c.) in the presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate (2 g.). The mixture was filtered and the filtrate evaporated to dryness and the residue crystallised from rectified spirit as light yellow needles, m.p. 171-72°. Its alcoholic solution gives a reddish brown colouration with ferric chloride solution. It does not easily dissolve in caustic alkali solution in the cold, but on boiling dissolves giving a greenish yellow solution. [Found in a sample dried over P₂O₅ in *vacuum* at 100-10°: C, 68.52; H, 4.93; OMe, 20.36. * C₁₅H₉O₃(OMe)₂ requires C, 68.45; H, 4.69; OMe, 20.81 per cent].

Monoacetylpuddumetin Monomethyl Ether (5-Acetoxy-7 : 4'-dimethoxyflavone).—It was prepared from puddumetin monomethyl ether using acetic anhydride and pyridine. It crystallised from dilute alcohol as colourless silky needles, m.p. 194-96°. An alcoholic solution of this compound does not give any colouration with ferric chloride solution, nor does it dissolve in cold caustic alkali solution. [Found in a sample dried over P_2O_5 in vacuum at 120-30° : C, 67.35; H, 4.9; OMe, 18.13. $C_{17}H_{16}O_4(OMe)_2$ requires C, 67.06; H, 4.70; OMe, 18.24 per cent). Monoacetylgenkwanin monomethyl ether melts at 199°.

Attempted aerial oxidation of Puddumetin.—Air was aspirated for 2 hours through a solution of puddumetin in dilute potassium hydroxide solution. The solution was left overnight and on acidification the solid was collected and crystallised from dilute alcohol as yellow needles, m.p. 278-80° (mixed m.p. with puddumetin 278-80°).

Alkaline Hydrolysis of Puddumetin : Isolation of p-Hydroxyacetophenone.—A solution of puddumetin (0.2 g.) in alcoholic potassium hydroxide (12.5 g. potassium hydroxide, 25 c.c. water, 30 c.c. rectified spirit) was refluxed for 14 hours on a boiling water-bath. The alcohol was then completely recovered from the solution, the solution was cooled and extracted with ether. The ethereal solution on evaporation left no residue. The alkaline solution was acidified and the solid separating was collected. The yellow acidic filtrate was preserved (A). The solid was treated with sodium bicarbonate solution and the pink insoluble residue was crystallised from dilute alcohol as a brownish solid, m.p. above 270°, which seemed to be unchanged puddumetin. The sodium bicarbonate solution on acidification and extraction with ether gave a very small quantity of a brown solid which could not be crystallised.

The acidic filtrate (A) was extracted with 50 c.c. of ether (in three instalments), the ether evaporated and the pasty brown solid was dissolved in potassium hydroxide solution, carbon dioxide was passed through the solution and the turbid solution extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was dried and ether removed when a small quantity of oil was left which solidified on cooling in ice. It was distilled in vacuum, and the thick liquid boiling at 95°/0.1 mm. solidified to a crystalline mass, m.p. 99-100°. It crystallised from benzene as colourless shining prisms, m.p. 102.5° (mixed m.p. with an authentic sample of *p*-hydroxyacetophenone) (semicarbazone, m.p. 192-93°, mixed m.p. with the semicarbazone of *p*-hydroxyacetophenone).

Demethylation of Puddumetin with Hydriodic Acid: Isolation of Apigenin.—Puddumetin (0.1 g.) was heated for 3 hours at 130-40° in a glycerine bath with hydriodic acid (sp. gr. 1.7, 10 c.c.) in an atmosphere of carbon dioxide. The mixture was diluted with water and the dark solid separating was collected, washed with sodium thiosulphate solution and water and crystallised from dilute alcohol as light yellow crystals, m.p. 344-46°, yield 0.07 g. Its alcoholic solution gives a dark brown colouration with ferric chloride and when reduced with magnesium and hydrochloric acid in alcoholic solution, it gives a light orange colour.

Triacetylapiogenin.—The above demethylated product was acylated with acetic anhydride and pyridine in the usual manner. It crystallises from dilute alcohol as colourless shining silky needles, m.p. 181-82°. (Found : C, 63.80; H, 4.49. Calc. for $C_{21}H_{16}O_8$: C, 63.63; H, 4.04 per cent).

All analyses recorded in this paper are micro-analyses, carried out by Mr. N. Ghosh, to whom our best thanks are due.